

Management

MOBILE SUBSCRIBERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS SERVICE TARIFF WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TUTICORIN DIST

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ABSTRACT

As it is a competitive world, Price plays a significant role in marketing. Increasing competition in this sector has led the providers to recognize the need to focus on the price of the service to retain the present customers. Normally, consumers think about the cost of the service or goods. After that only, they will consider about quality, colour, size and other features. Consumers may choose the mobile service provider in the tariff base. Thus, tariff influences in selecting mobile service provider. This study focuses on significance of service tariff in the satisfaction of the subscribers in Tuticorin Dist.

Keywords:

Subscribers, Competition, Mobile, Communication & Tariff.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Communication is used to exchange and express our messages, facts, ideas, opinion, feelings and so on. We can say that without communication we cannot live comfortably. Communication is the life blood of social as well as business world. Because of communication, we can exit in the world. It is the right to say that our world is communication world. This is the communication era. Such a great communication started with different ways and modes. Our ancient people used pigeon, horse and human beings to bring the information from one place to another place. But the practical difficulties were not covering the distance and many persons. Then telegraph came and used to pass the information fast and distance places. After that telephone did such a great and fast communication. Now, we have very fast communication in the form of Mobile communication. Due to technology, we have lots of communication channels. They are E- mail, telephone, postal, Medias, mobile and fax. Out of these, mobile has a significant role and important place in communication.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To evaluate the factors influencing in relation to service tariff.
- To study the subscribers' attitude towards services tariff.
- To identify the problems those are being faced by the subscribers.
- To offer suggestions to fix reasonable charges.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

These days, people change the service providers frequently. There are so many reasons behind that. If a customer does not get satisfaction towards a particular service provider, immediately, he/she wants to switch over from their existing one to newer one. And also nowadays, there is facility that is any subscribers can switch over from any service provider to other without changing their old number. According TRAI, after implementing this MNP scheme, many of subscribers switched over. Whatever it may be, first of all, the customer focus on the price of goods or service. There is no exception for mobile communication service. Here also, the subscribers mostly worry about the tariff rates and hidden cost. Tariff is charged for the providing mobile communication service. Reasonable tariff is one of the significant components of retaining the subscribers and getting new subscribers. Every subscriber has the right to get proper and standard service at a reasonable tariff. Over the last decades, tariff is decreasing silently for every day. There is no possibility to remember the balance at every time. In that context, this study has been done, to find out the impact of service tariff among the mobile subscribers in Tuticorin Dist.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is confined to the service tariff of mobile service communication in Tuticorin District. In Tuticorin District there are good numbers of mobile subscribers in both urban and rural areas, having advanced equipment. Both the government and private service providers have been included in this study. Further, the study is confined to factors that influence the subscribers to select a particular service operator and the subscribers' attitudes towards various mobile service providers in terms of service tariff. As regards subscribers' attitude towards tariff, the study is confined to the problems that are faced by them in terms of service tariff mobile communication services.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF SERVICE TARIFF

The service tariff is another very important factor to determine the satisfaction of the subscribers. The service tariff charges by the service providers for the services used by the subscriber. Usually, the subscribers are very keen on updating the service tariff. Thus, the level of satisfaction of service tariff of the respondents is presented below.

Table 1: Level of satisfaction of service tariff of the respondents

Service Tariff			HDS	DS	N	S	HS	Total
Call Tariff	Public sector	Count	15	22	56	9	2	104
		% Within	14.4	21.1	53.9	8.7	1.9	100
	Private sector	Count	70	99	179	194	80	622
		% Within	11.2	15.9	28.8	31.1	13	100
Caller Tune Charge	Public sector	Count	7	19	29	49	0	104
		% Within	6.7	18.2	27.9	47.2	0	100
	Private sector	Count	81	84	140	200	117	622
		% Within	13	13.5	22.5	32.2	18.8	100
SMS Charge	Public sector	Count	5	30	15	51	3	104
		% Within	4.8	28.9	14.4	49	2.9	100
	Private sector	Count	53	77	139	262	91	622
		% Within	8.5	12.4	22.3	42.2	14.6	100
Festival SMS Charge	Public sector	Count	31	3	68	1	1	104
		% Within	29.8	2.9	65.3	1	1	100
	Private sector	Count	286	105	142	54	35	622
		% Within	46	16.9	22.8	8.7	5.6	100
VAS Charges	Public sector	Count	28	34	31	2	9	104
		% Within	26.9	32.7	29.8	1.9	8.7	100
	Private sector	Count	216	117	127	90	72	622
		% Within	34.7	18.8	20.4	14.5	11.6	100
Internet Charge	Public sector	Count	7	18	31	40	8	104
		% Within	6.7	17.3	29.8	38.5	7.7	100
	Private sector	Count	66	119	166	211	60	622
		% Within	10.6	19.1	26.8	33.9	9.6	100

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that:

- a) **Call tariff:** In the public sector, 53.9 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 21.1 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 14.4 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied, 8.7 percent of the respondents are satisfied and 1.9 per cent of the respondents are highly satisfied with call tariff. In the private sector, 31.1 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 28.8 percent of the respondents are neutral, 15.9 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 13 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied and 11.2 per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with call tariff charged by the service provider.

It is inferred that 53.9 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 31.1 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with call tariff.

- b) **Caller tune charge:** In the public sector, 47.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 27.9 percent of the respondents are neutral, 18.2 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 6.7 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with caller tune charges. In the private sector, 32.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 22.5 percent of the respondents are

neutral, 18.8 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 13.5 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 13 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied.

It is inferred that 47.2 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 32.2 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied with caller tune charges.

c) **SMS charges:** In the public sector, 49 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 28.9 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 14.4 percent of the respondents are neutral, 4.8 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and 2.9 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied with SMS charges. In the private sector, 42.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 22.3 percent of the respondents are neutral, 14.6 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 12.4 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 8.5 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with SMS charges.

It is inferred that 49 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 42.2 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with SMS charges.

d) **Festival SMS charges:** In the public sector, 65.3 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 29.8 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied 2.9 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied and one per cent of the respondents are highly satisfied as well as satisfied with festival SMS charges. In the private sector, 46 per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied, 22.8 percent of the respondents are neutral, 16.9 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 8.7 percent of the respondents are satisfied and 5.6 per cent of the respondents are highly satisfied with festival SMS charges.

It is inferred that 65.3 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 46 per cent of the private sector respondents are highly dissatisfied with festival SMS charges.

e) **Value Added Service (VAS):** In the public sector, 32.7 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 29.8 percent of the respondents are neutral, 26.9 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied, 8.7 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied and 1.9 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with value added services. In the private sector, 34.7 per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied, 20.4 percent of the respondents are neutral, 18.8 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 14.5 percent of the respondents are satisfied and 11.6 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied with value added services.

It is inferred that 32.7 per cent of the public sector respondents are dissatisfied and 34.7 percent of the private sector respondents are dissatisfied with other value added services.

f) **Internet charges:** In the public sector, 38.5 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 29.8 percent of the respondents are neutral, 17.3 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 7.7 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied and 6.7 per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with internet charges. In the private sector, 33.9 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 26.8 percent of the respondents are neutral, 19.1 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 10.6 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and 9.6 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied with internet charges.

It is inferred that 38.5 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 33.9 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with internet charges.

g) Ranking on factors Influencing satisfaction towards service tariff

In service tariff, we have six different factors. Out of that, which factor is mostly influenced on satisfaction of the respondents is discussed. It is clearly explained in the following table 5.23.

Table 2: Ranking on factors Influencing satisfaction on service tariff

Service Tariff	Public sector		Private sector	
	Mean scores	Rank	Mean scores	Rank
Call Tariff	2.62	IV	3.18	III
Caller Tune Charge	3.15	III	3.30	II
SMS Charge	3.16	II	3.41	I
Festival SMS Charge	2.40	V	2.11	VI
VAS Charges	2.32	VI	2.49	V
Internet Charge	3.23	I	3.12	IV

Source: Computed Primary Data

From the above table it is clear that internet charge has the first rank followed by SMS Charge, caller tune charge, call tariff, festival SMS charge and value added services, whereas in private sector SMS charge is ranked first, followed by caller tune charge, call tariff, internet charge, value added charge and festival SMS charge.

It is inferred that in public sector internet charge influences of satisfaction, whereas in private sector SMS charge influences more on satisfaction of the respondents.

6. FINDINGS

- It is inferred that 53.9 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 31.1 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with call tariff.
- It is inferred that 47.2 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 32.2 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied with caller tune charges.
- It is inferred that 49 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 42.2 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with SMS charges.
- It is inferred that 65.3 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 46 per cent of the private sector respondents are highly dissatisfied with festival SMS charges.
- It is inferred that 32.7 per cent of the public sector respondents are dissatisfied and 34.7 percent of the private sector respondents are dissatisfied with other value added services.

- It is inferred that 38.5 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 33.9 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with internet charges.
- It is inferred that in public sector internet charge influences of satisfaction, whereas in private sector SMS charge influences more on satisfaction of the respondents.

7. CONCLUSION

As money plays many and major role in today's marketing, nowadays customers are very clear about their spending amount. If they have to pay more to get the service from the particular service provider, then they switch over from their current service providers to other service providers. There should not be any high amount of price to the product and service. And also the service providers must try to provide proper service at a reasonable tariff. Sometimes the subscribers may think that the service may not worthy for given tariff by the subscribers. Whatever maybe, it is the duty and right of the service operator has to supply better service at a practical tariff.

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